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Breeding for Post-Harvest Physiological Deterioration in Cassava Genotypes at Otobi, Sub-station of NRCRI, Umudike

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted at the Nationally Coordinated Research Project of breeding stage and was evaluated at National Root Crops Research Institute, Otobi sub-station to investigate breeding for Post-Harvest Physiological Deterioration in Cassava Genotypes. Twelve yellow root cassava genotypes were used for this study. The experimental layout was a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications. The aim of the study is to evaluate the levels of PPD in yellow-root cassava genotypes at 7 and 14 days after harvest. Data collected were subjected to percentage means, Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and correlated analysis using GENSTAT software. Results showed that genotype (G10) had the highest percentage mean of 6.17% at 7 days after harvest while genotype G3 shows the highest percentage mean of 8.81% at 14 DAH. Total carotenoid ranged from 5.63 to 13.79µg/g (fresh weight basis) while dry matter ranged from 19.8 to 37.7%. Root colour shows 2.67 to 5.67. The study concluded that, there was one genotype (G12) with an average PPD value of zero across the two evaluation dates, which also implies the tolerant genotype for PPD, hence, good for commercial root for both the farmers and processors.

Keywords: yellow-flesh cassava, post-harvest physiological deterioration, genotype, design, environment

INTRODUCTION

Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) is a starchy root crop that is among the most important tropical food crops in the world. It provides the food energy intake for nearly a billion people in 105 countries worldwide and is considered as the cheapest source of starch used in more than 300 industrial products ("Cassava for Food," 2008). A serious constraint to cassava production is the short shelf-life of its roots due to post-harvest physiological deterioration (PPD). PPD is triggered by the inevitable wounding that occurs during harvesting and handling, and is characterized by a rapid discolouration of cassava roots that starts within 24 hours after harvest. The discolouration appears first in the vascular system around the wounds (Reilly, *et al.*, 2007), from where it spreads to the rest of the root. The PPD phenomenon makes cassava root highly perishable commodity that cannot be delivered and marketed easily. It is estimated that in some of the major cassava producing countries, 10% to 20% of the cassava roots are lost due to the PPD (Shi, *et al.*, 2016). One of the major constraints is that cassava roots have a short post-harvest shelf life, which severely limits their potential in the market and their benefits to cassava farmers. The roots exhibit visible symptoms of post-harvest physiological deterioration (PPD) within only 24 to 72 hours of

harvest (Morante *et al.*, 2010; Vanderschuren *et al.*, 2014). The deterioration of cassava roots generally starts with a black-blue to black vascular discoloration (vascular streaking) which quickly spreads to the parenchyma tissue. PPD results in sizeable quantitative and striking qualitative post-harvest losses of the fresh cassava roots. Post-harvest losses are major factors contributing to food insecurity and significant monetary losses among cassava farmers, especially in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) (Abass *et al.*, 2014). In response to such problems, traditional efforts and practices have been employed to reduce the losses due to cassava perishability in SSA. However, most of these practices increase production costs; restrict the crops to a small market share, and only address issues related subsistence forms of farming (Nasser and Ortiz, 2010). Therefore, efforts to reduce such losses are required if cassava is to move to extended markets, including industrial application. This will greatly contribute to improved food security in areas where cassava is staple crop. Reduction of such losses also has a positive impact on economic security of value chain actors engaged in storage and processing of cassava roots and their production. According to Zidenga *et al.*, (2012), there have been efforts to improve some of these characteristics through breeding; such efforts have not provided a wholesome variety that would address all loss factors along the value chain. The objectives of this research are (i) to identify and evaluate cassava genotypes for yield and PPD tolerance; (ii) to further identify cassava genotypes that exhibit reduction/delayed PPD potential.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Twelve cassava genotypes collected from National Root Crops Research Institute, Umudike was established at Otobi, Sub-station, Otukpo, Benue State, in 2019 and 2020 cropping seasons with vegetation type: Southern guinea Savannah, Longitude: 04° 53'E, Latitude 08° 26'N. The mean annual rainfall ranges from 800mm to 1712mm with temperature ranges from 21°C to 36°C with relative humidity ranged from 65% to 87%; laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications. Plot size of 5rows x7plants (35m²), a planting distance of 0.8m x 1m inter and intra row spacing gave a total plant population of 10,000 plants/ha. Weeding of trial was done manually at 5 weeks after planting, 3MAP and 9MAP respectively before harvesting. Pre-harvest and post-harvest data at 6&9MAP were evaluated which includes growth and yield parameters and PPD evaluation.

Statistical analysis

The data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using General Linear Model (GLM) procedure in Genstat Discovery edition 17th (Genstat, 2014) to test for the treatment of effect and significant interaction of the variables considered.

RESULTS

The result of the girth produced revealed that genotype G9 (3.10cm) was significantly higher than the rest of the genotypes. However, G1 (2.23cm) and G7 (2.23cm) gave statistically lower values. The reaction of the genotypes to plant height revealed that G2 (230.0 m) is significantly higher than other evaluated genotypes while G12 recorded the lowest plant height of 143.3m (Table 1); Plant type shows that G5 was statistically better than others with a value of 5.17 while the least value of 2.00 was recorded by G6 (Table 1); for branch height, the data showed that genotypes G10 and G11 recorded branch height value of 75.0m respectively and are higher statistically than others while G5 gave the least value of 20.0m (Table 1). The reaction of selected yellow genotypes to root shape revealed that G1, G2, G4 and G6 were significantly higher with a value of 3.00 respectively while G8 and G12 recorded the lowest value of 1.67 root shape (Table 1); root size indicate that G7 and G10 were significantly higher with value 5.67 respectively while G12 recorded the least value of 2.00 (Table 1); the branch level showed that G3 and G6 performed significantly than other genotypes with a value of 7.00 m respectively while G5 revealed the lowest value of 2.17 m (Table 1).

Dry matter content (DMC) ranged from 19.80 to 37.70% across the selected genotypes. Genotype (G6) had the highest DMC of 37.70% which is significantly ($P < 0.05$) different from the rest while, G12 recorded the least value of 19.80%. Nine genotypes had DMC more than above the grand mean (30.6%) while three yielded less than the grand mean, (Table 2). Dry matter content is a very important trait for

acceptability of the cassava by consumers. Dry root yield (DRY) showed that G4 (5.90 t/ha) was significantly higher than the rest of the genotypes. G8 (1.72 t/ha), G11 (1.65 t/ha) and G9 (1.47 t/ha) gave statistically lower after evaluation. Six genotypes yielded below the grand mean (2.85 t/ha) (Table 2). The Fresh root yield (FRY) ranged from 4.9 t/ha to 18.5t/ha. Genotypes (G4) had the highest FRY of 18.5 t/ha while G11 recorded the least value of 4.9 t/ha. Five genotypes had FRY more than above the grand mean (8.9 t/ha) while six yielded less than the grand mean, (Table 2). Harvest index (HI) ranged from 0.27 to 0.59. Genotype (G4) had the highest HI value of 0.59 while G12 recorded the least HI value of 0.27. Seven genotypes had HI more than above the grand mean (0.43) while four genotypes produced less than the grand mean value (Table 2). Starch content ranged from 10.13% to 25.88% starch. Genotype (G6) had the highest value of 25.88% while G12 recorded the least value of 10.13%. Seven genotypes had starch content more than above the grand mean value (Table 2). The reaction of yellow root cassava genotypes to post-harvest physiological deterioration at 7 days after harvest (DAH) ranged from 0.00 to 6.17% with a grand mean of 3.13% (Table 3). At 7 DAH, genotype (G10) statistically revealed a PPD mean value of 6.17% higher while, the least value of 0.00% PPD was obtained for G12. Six genotypes had PPD more than above the grand mean (3.13%) while six genotypes recorded less than the grand mean (Table 3). PPD at 14DAH ranged from 0.00 in genotype (G12) to 8.81 in genotype (G3). Six genotypes had scores of more than the grand mean (5.45) while, six had less than the grand mean (Table 3). Root colour (RTCOL) ranged from 2.67 to 5.67 with a grand mean of 4.42. Genotype (G6) had the highest value of 5.67 while genotype (G12) revealed statistically lowest value of 2.67. Six genotypes had RTCOL more than above the grand mean (4.42) while six had less than the grand mean (Table 3). Total Carotene content (TCC) ranged from 5.63µg/g to 13.79µg/g. Genotype (G9) statistically recorded the highest TCC value of 13.79µg/g while genotype (G5) had the least value of 5.63µg/g. Seven genotypes had TCC more than above the grand mean (10.70µg/g) while, five genotypes revealed less than the grand mean (Table 3).

Table 1: Mean performance of selected yellow root cassava genotypes evaluated for Pre-harvest data at Otobi sub-station.

Genotypes	GIRTH (cm)	PLTHGT (m)	PLTTYPE	BRNHGT	RTSHAPE	RTSIZE	BRNLVL
G1	2.23 ^b	166.7 ^{ebdc}	2.83 ^{ed}	53.3 ^{ba}	3.00 ^a	4.33 ^{bcd}	6.83 ^c
G10	2.53 ^{ba}	197.0 ^{ba}	3.83 ^{bdc}	75.0	2.00 ^a	5.67 ^d	4.67 ^{bc}
G11	2.63 ^{ba}	220.0 ^a	4.50 ^{bac}	75.0 ^a	2.67 ^a	3.67 ^{abc}	6.67 ^c
G12	2.67 ^{ba}	143.3 ^e	2.83 ^{ed}	45.0 ^{ba}	1.67 ^a	2.00 ^a	6.17 ^c
G2	2.53 ^{ba}	230.0 ^a	4.83 ^{ba}	73.3 ^a	3.00 ^a	4.33 ^{bcd}	2.33 ^{ab}
G3	2.70 ^{ba}	168.3 ^{ebdc}	3.00 ^{ed}	45.7 ^{ba}	2.00 ^a	3.67 ^{abc}	7.00 ^c
G4	2.70 ^{ba}	151.7 ^{edc}	3.83 ^{bdc}	46.7 ^{ba}	3.00 ^a	5.00 ^{cd}	5.67 ^c
G5	2.63 ^{ba}	193.3 ^{bac}	5.17 ^a	20.0 ^b	2.00 ^a	3.67 ^{abc}	2.17 ^a
G6	2.60 ^{ba}	188.3 ^{bdac}	2.00 ^e	45.0 ^{ba}	3.00 ^a	3.00 ^{ab}	7.00 ^c
G7	2.23 ^b	146.7 ^{ed}	3.50 ^{dc}	65.0 ^{ba}	2.33 ^a	5.67 ^d	5.33 ^c
G8	2.37 ^{ba}	186.7 ^{ebdac}	3.50 ^{dc}	70.0 ^a	1.67 ^a	3.67 ^{abc}	6.00 ^c
G9	3.10 ^a	153.3 ^{edc}	3.00 ^{ed}	58.3 ^{ba}	2.67 ^a	4.33 ^{bcd}	6.83 ^c
Grand mean	2.58	178.8	3.57	56.0	2.42	4.08	5.56
S.E.D	0.22	7.63	0.12	5.32	0.22	0.25	0.49
CV %	8.4	4.3	3.4	9.5	9.1	6.1	8.9
LSD (0.05)	0.76	43.44	1.06	47.37	1.45	1.93	2.42

Means with the same letter are not significantly different: Girth (cm), PLTHGT: plant height (m), BRNLVL: branch level (cm), RTSHAPE: root shape, RT SIZE: root size, BRNHGT: branch height, S.E.D: standard errors of differences of means, CV: coefficient of variation %

Table 2: Mean performance of selected yellow root cassava genotypes evaluated for root yields and its components at Otobi sub-station.

Means with the same letters are not significantly different: FRY: fresh root yield (t/ha), DMC: dry matter

Genotypes	DMC %	DRY(t/ha)	FRY (t/ha)	HI	STARCH %
G1	31.7 ^{bac}	2.86 ^{ba}	9.0 ^{ba}	0.51 ^{ba}	17.89 ^{abcde}
G10	30.9 ^{bac}	3.64 ^{ba}	11.8 ^{ba}	0.54 ^{ba}	16.81 ^{abcd}
G11	35.3 ^a	1.65 ^b	4.9 ^b	0.37 ^{bc}	22.68 ^{de}
G12	19.8 ^c	1.72 ^b	5.9 ^b	0.27 ^c	10.13 ^a
G2	32.6 ^{ba}	3.50 ^{ba}	10.9 ^{ba}	0.44 ^{bac}	19.11 ^{bcde}
G3	27.5 ^{bac}	1.46 ^b	5.3 ^b	0.39 ^{bac}	12.33 ^{abc}
G4	32.7 ^a	5.90 ^a	18.5 ^a	0.59 ^a	19.25 ^{bcde}
G5	34.4 ^a	4.76 ^{ba}	13.4 ^{ba}	0.49 ^{bac}	21.46 ^{de}
G6	37.7 ^a	2.56 ^{ba}	6.7 ^b	0.32 ^{bc}	25.88 ^e
G7	33.8 ^a	3.01 ^{ba}	8.9 ^{ba}	0.51 ^{ba}	20.68 ^{cde}
G8	31.0 ^{bac}	1.72 ^b	5.6 ^b	0.33 ^{bc}	16.97 ^{abcd}
G9	20.3 ^{bc}	1.47 ^b	5.8 ^b	0.44 ^{bac}	10.80 ^{ab}
Grand mean	30.6	2.85	8.9	0.43	17.83
S.E.D	2.92	0.58	2.03	0.05	1.80
CV %	9.5	2.4	22.9	10.6	10.1
LSD (0.05)	12.38	3.50	10.93	0.23	8.59

content (%), DRY: dry root yield (t/ha), HI: harvest index, S.E.D: standard errors of differences of means, CV: coefficient of variation

Table 3: Mean performance of selected yellow root cassava genotypes evaluated for PPD at 7, 14 DAH, root colour and total carotene content at Otobi sub-station.

Genotypes	PPD(7DAH)	PPD (14DAH)	RTCOL	TCC (µg/g)
G1	2.18 ^{ba}	3.50 ^{ba}	5.00 ^{cd}	10.73 ^g
G10	6.17 ^a	6.85 ^{ba}	5.00 ^{cd}	10.59 ⁱ
G11	2.48 ^{ba}	5.16 ^{ba}	4.00 ^{bc}	12.08 ^e
G12	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	2.67 ^a	7.01 ^k
G2	6.02 ^a	7.92 ^{ba}	5.00 ^{cd}	8.02 ^j
G3	4.50 ^{ba}	8.81 ^a	4.33 ^{bc}	13.00 ^c
G4	1.98 ^{ba}	6.16 ^{ba}	5.00 ^{cd}	13.02 ^b
G5	2.12 ^{ba}	7.24 ^{ba}	3.33 ^{ab}	5.63 ^l
G6	4.23 ^{ba}	4.31 ^{ba}	5.67 ^{cd}	12.92 ^d
G7	3.20 ^{ba}	8.47 ^a	4.00 ^{bc}	10.98 ^f
G8	3.36 ^{ba}	3.32 ^{ba}	4.00 ^{bc}	10.69 ^h
G9	1.32 ^{ba}	3.63 ^{ba}	5.00 ^{cd}	13.79 ^a
Grand mean	3.13	5.45	4.42	10.70
S.E.D	0.41	0.72	0.22	0.00
CV %	13.1	13.1	5.0	0.00
LSD (0.05)	4.95	7.93	1.22	1.22

Means with the same letters are not significantly different: PPD: Post harvest physiology deterioration at 7 and 14 days after harvest, RTCOL: root colour: TCC: total carotene content, S.E.D: standard errors of differences of means, CV: coefficient of variation

CONCLUSION

The results showed that six cassava genotypes with low PPD in order of superiority were G12, G9, G4, G5, G1, and G11. According to the findings of Tumuhimbise *et al.*, (2014), the low values of PPD observed in the yellow root genotypes point to deliberate actions by the breeding programme to select for genotypes with low PPD, and hence, higher shelf-life. In addition, one genotype (G12) with an average PPD of zero across the two evaluation dates implies the tolerant genotype in this study.

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